

A NOVEL PROCEDURE FOR DAMAGE EVALUATION OF FILLET-WELDED JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, a novel procedure for fatigue resistance assessment of fillet-welded joints under complex random loading is proposed. It consists of two consecutive steps: (1) computation of the stress tensor at the verification point; (2) evaluation of damage and, consequently, fatigue life. The procedure exploits the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al. for random loading. A case study, represented by a mechanical component of an arm sprayer used in agriculture, is examined in order to assess such a procedure. A comparison between experimental and numerical results in terms of crack nucleation location is performed.

KEYWORDS: critical plane, hot spot, multiaxial, random loading

NOMENCLATURE

\mathbf{C}	vector lying on the critical plane
C_a^*	amplitude of \mathbf{C}^* in a given reversal
\mathbf{C}_i	vector series of \mathbf{C}
\mathbf{C}_i^*	reduced vector series of \mathbf{C}
C_u, C_v	components of \mathbf{C} along the directions \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} , respectively
$C_{u,i}, C_{v,i}$	scalar series of the modulus of the \mathbf{C} components
$D(T_0)$	damage accumulated during the observation period T_0
D_{cr}	critical damage
F_b, F_c	forces applied to the H component FE model
F_b^m, F_c^m	forces applied to the H component FE model in order to simulate the m -th maneuver
H	Hot spot
m	maneuver number (see Table 1)
n	number of elements of both \mathbf{N} - and \mathbf{C} -series
\mathbf{N}	vector perpendicular to the critical plane
N_i	scalar series of the \mathbf{N} modulus
N_i^*	reduced scalar series of \mathbf{N}
N_{\max}^*	maximum value of \mathbf{N}^* in a given reversal
Ora	polar frame
\mathbf{S}_w	stress vector at the verification point
T	plate thickness or thickness of both the chord and the brace for the case study examined
T_f	fatigue life
T_0	observation period
\bar{T}	observation time interval for the case study examined
uvw	local frame attached to the critical plane
XYZ	fixed frame

\mathbf{w}	normal to the critical plane
W	weight function
$W1, W2, W3$	control points
$\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$	averaged principal stress directions

α	orientation of a generic extrapolation path
δ	angle between $\hat{1}$ and \mathbf{w}
$\varepsilon_{1,b}^{exp,m}$	experimental maximum principal strain time-history at point W3
$\varepsilon_{1,b}^{num}$	numerical maximum principal strain at point W3 computed for $F_b = 1N$
$\varepsilon_{1,c}^{exp,m}$	experimental maximum principal strain time-history at point W1, or equivalently, at point W2
$\varepsilon_{1,c}^{num}$	numerical maximum principal strain at point W1 computed for $F_c = 1N$
ϕ, θ, ψ	principal Euler angles
$\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi}$	averaged principal Euler angles
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	fatigue strength under fully reversed normal stress (evaluated at N_0 loading cycles)
$\sigma_{eq,a}^{(j)}$	amplitude of the equivalent stress related to the j -th reversal
$\sigma_{x,hs}$	σ_x at the hot spot
$\sigma_{y,hs}$	σ_y at the hot spot
$\tau_{xy,hs}$	τ_{xy} at the hot spot
$\sigma_{1,max}$	maximum value of the maximum principal stress σ_1
$\tau_{af,-1}$	fatigue strength under fully reversed shear stress (evaluated at N_0^* loading cycles)

1. INTRODUCTION

Fillet-welded joints, in the form of "T" joint, lap joint and corner joint, represent the most common connections in welded structures. Fillet-welded joints combine different advantages such as lightness of structures, high flexibility in geometrical design, and cost saving due to both reduced fabrication time and less manufacture effort. Despite of this, fillet-welded joints can also represent the weakest part of welded structures with respect to failure, since their breakdown is generally due to fatigue-induced failure, approximatively in 90% of cases [1]. Data in the literature cover different fatigue failure modes [1,2], the most common ones under service conditions being produced by crack initiation and propagation (a) at weld toes and running into the parent material, (b) at weld root and running into the weld throat, and (c) at discontinuities inside the weld and running into welding/parent material.

For welded structures under simple cyclic loading (i.e. tension-compression or cyclic bending or others), international fatigue design rules employing procedures based on fatigue strength S-N curves are now widely available [3-5], although local stress approach and crack initiation-based fatigue life approach represent alternatives for fatigue life evaluation related to welded structures [6-8].

More precisely, according to the "Recommendations for fatigue design of welded joints and components" [5], the above procedures based on fatigue strength S-N curves differ from each other for the

stress range (computed or measured) employed to perform such an assessment. Three approaches have been proposed in Ref.[5]: (i) nominal stress approach, (ii) structural hot spot stress approach, (iii) effective notch stress approach.

As a matter of fact, the stress range may include or exclude the local stress raising effect coming from (1) discontinuity due to a structural detail of welded joint and (2) weld toe transition. More precisely:

(i) Nominal stress approach: the stress range is computed or measured by excluding the local stress raising effect due to both discontinuity and transition;

(ii) Structural hot spot stress approach: the stress range is computed or measured by including the local stress raising effect due to the above discontinuity, but excluding that due to the above transition;

(iii) Effective notch stress approach: the stress range is computed or measured by including the local stress raising effect due to both discontinuity and transition.

Figure 1 shows the stress computed at a given time instant, according to the above three approaches.

Figure 1.

Note that, when large cutouts are present in the vicinity of the welded joint, their local stress raising effects have to be included in the computed or measured stress range.

For welded structures under complex cyclic loading (i.e. multiaxial), the most common design approaches are based on the maximum principal stress range or equivalent stress range, then referred to fatigue strength S-N curves, the same ones used for welded structures under simple cyclic loading [9]. However, there are extensive experimental data showing that the above approaches can overestimate the fatigue life of welded structures even by an order of magnitude under non-proportional loading [9]. As a matter of fact, fatigue life under non-proportional loading decreases with respect to that under proportional loading, and that is due to: (i) additional hardening effect, or (ii) initiation of more micro-cracks produced by the activation of more slip systems in grains, as a consequence of the change of principal stress/strain directions. Therefore, when a given approach does not take into account the above phenomena, fatigue life may be overestimated. This drawback has prompted the research work towards the development of alternative methods to be used in fatigue assessment of welded structures under complex cyclic loading [10-30].

In such a context, a novel procedure for fatigue resistance assessment of fillet-welded joints under complex random loading is herein proposed. Such a procedure consists of two consecutive steps: (1) computation of the stress tensor at the verification point (hot spot), according to the extrapolation equation derived through the structural hot spot stress approach [5]; (2) evaluation of damage (at the same verification point) and, consequently fatigue life, by applying the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri

et al. for random loading [31-34]. To the best knowledge of the authors, a similar procedure has not been proposed in the literature yet.

In order to verify the above novel procedure, data available in the literature are employed [35-39]. More precisely, a fillet-welded structure represented by the H component of an arm sprayer used in agriculture is analysed (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2.

As a matter of fact, the H component is constituted from welded tubular elements, fillet-welded as T-joints. Each joint consists of two tubular elements: one with a rectangular cross-section, named chord, and the other one with a circular cross-section, named brace. Under the arm sprayer service condition, the whole H component is subjected to high-cycle random fatigue loading and, consequently, each of its T-joints experiences a multiaxial random stress field.

The novel procedure is applied to that T-joint of the H component where fatigue failure is experimentally observed (**Figure 3**), in order to evaluate the region on the weld toe where cracks are expected to nucleate.

Figure 3.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 is dedicated to the description of the novel procedure. In Section 3, the case study is presented by giving details on the geometry and the stress field

that characterise the fillet T-joint examined, and on the damage evaluation. The results obtained are discussed in Section 4, and conclusions are summarised in Section 5.

2. THE NOVEL PROCEDURE

Firstly, the proposed procedure requires to compute the stress state at the verification point and then the accumulated damage at the same point.

2.1 Computation of the stress tensor components at the verification point

Let us consider the point H in **Figure 4**, assumed as the hot spot, and the extrapolation path perpendicular to the weld **[5]**.

Figure 4.

The stress state at a generic point along the above path is biaxial, that is, the stress tensor components different from zero are σ_x, σ_y , and τ_{xy} . In order to compute the values of such components at the hot spot, the extrapolation equation derived through the structural hot spot stress approach for type "a" hot spot and coarse mesh **[5]** is employed, that is:

$$\sigma_{x,hs} = 1.5\sigma_{x(0.5T)} - 0.5\sigma_{x(1.5T)} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{y,hs} = 1.5\sigma_{y(0.5T)} - 0.5\sigma_{y(1.5T)} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_{xy,hs} = 1.5\tau_{xy(0.5T)} - 0.5\tau_{xy(1.5T)} \quad (3)$$

where the stresses with the subscripts $0.5T$ and $1.5T$ are those at two reference points which are $0.5T$ and $1.5T$ away from H along the extrapolation path, respectively, being T the plate thickness.

2.2 Damage and fatigue life computation

In order to compute damage and consequently the fatigue life, the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al. for random loading, formulated in time-domain, is employed [31-34]. The criterion is here applied in the form that implements the recent modifications proposed in Ref. [34].

Let us consider a verification point and a fixed frame XYZ with its origin in such a point. According to the above criterion, the principal Euler angles ϕ, θ, ψ at the verification point are averaged as follows:

$$\hat{\phi} = \frac{1}{W} \int_0^{T_0} \phi(t) W(t) dt \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{W} \int_0^{T_0} \theta(t) W(t) dt \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{\psi} = \frac{1}{W} \int_0^{T_0} \psi(t) W(t) dt \quad (6)$$

where

$$W = \int_0^{T_0} W(t) dt \quad (7)$$

and the weight function $W(t)$ is given by:

$$H[x] = 1 \text{ for } x \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

$$W(t) = H[\sigma_1(t) - \sigma_{1,\max}] \quad H[x] = 0 \text{ for } x < 0$$

being $\sigma_{1,\max}$ the maximum value of the maximum principal stress $\sigma_1(t)$ during the observation period T_0 . By using the above angles $\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi}$, the averaged principal stress directions $\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$ are identified.

The normal \mathbf{w} to the critical plane is assumed to belong to the principal plane $\hat{1}\hat{3}$, and its direction is determined by rotating $\hat{1}$ -axis towards $\hat{3}$ -axis of an angle expressed by (in degrees):

$$\delta = \frac{3}{2} \left[1 - \left(\frac{\tau_{af,-1}}{\sigma_{af,-1}} \right)^2 \right] 45^\circ \quad (9)$$

where $\tau_{af,-1}$ is the fatigue strength under fully reversed shear stress (evaluated at N_0^* loading cycles), whereas $\sigma_{af,-1}$ is the fatigue strength under fully reversed normal stress (evaluated at N_0 loading cycles).

Once the critical plane passing through the verification point is identified, a local frame \mathbf{uvw} is adopted, where the \mathbf{u} -direction is represented by the intersection line between the critical plane and the \mathbf{wZ} plane, and \mathbf{v} forms an orthogonal frame with \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{w} . The stress vector \mathbf{S}_w at the verification point may be decomposed as follows:

$$\mathbf{S}_w = \mathbf{N} + \mathbf{C} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{N} is perpendicular to the critical plane, whereas \mathbf{C} lies on such a plane and may be decomposed in two components, C_u and C_v , along the directions \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} , respectively.

Let us consider the scalar series N_i of the modulus of \mathbf{N} , and the vector series \mathbf{C}_i of the vector \mathbf{C} , each series being composed by n elements (i.e. $0 \leq i \leq n$). Note that \mathbf{C} -series can be also equivalently represented by the two scalar series of its components, named $C_{u,i}$ and $C_{v,i}$.

A reduction procedure is performed on \mathbf{N} -series in order to preserve only peaks and valleys of this series, and a new one, named \mathbf{N}^* -series, is obtained. As an example, let us consider three terms of the \mathbf{N} -series, that is, N_i, N_{i+1} and N_{i+2} , where N_i is a peak and N_{i+2} is a valley, i.e. $N_i > N_{i+2}$. The indexes of the latter terms are registered in a vector of two components, $\mathbf{K} \equiv (k_1, k_2)$: in this case, we have $\mathbf{K} \equiv (i, i+2)$. The reduction procedure operates as follows:

$$N_i^* = N_{k_1} \qquad N_{i+1}^* = \frac{N_{k_1} + N_{k_2}}{2} \qquad N_{i+2}^* = N_{k_2} \qquad (11)$$

In such a way, the number of terms for the \mathbf{N} - and \mathbf{N}^* -series is the same and equal to n .

A reduction procedure is also performed on the \mathbf{C} -series in order to preserve only the vectors that maximise the amplitude of \mathbf{C} between a peak and a valley of the \mathbf{N} -series. In more detail, if we consider the above case, i.e. $\mathbf{K} \equiv (i, i+2)$, the following amplitudes are computed according to the definition by Papadopoulos [40]:

$$C_{a(i,i+1)} = \sqrt{\left[C_{u,i+1} - \frac{1}{2}(C_{u,i} + C_{u,i+1}) \right]^2 + \left[C_{v,i+1} - \frac{1}{2}(C_{v,i} + C_{v,i+1}) \right]^2} \qquad (12)$$

$$C_{a(i,i+2)} = \sqrt{\left[C_{u,i+2} - \frac{1}{2}(C_{u,i} + C_{u,i+2}) \right]^2 + \left[C_{v,i+2} - \frac{1}{2}(C_{v,i} + C_{v,i+2}) \right]^2} \quad (13)$$

Then, if $C_{a(i,i+1)} \leq C_{a(i,i+2)}$, we get:

$$C_i^* = C_{k_1} \quad C_{i+1}^* = \frac{C_{k_1} + C_{k_2}}{2} \quad C_{i+2}^* = C_{k_2} \quad (14)$$

whereas, if $C_{a(i,i+1)} > C_{a(i,i+2)}$, we get:

$$C_i^* = C_{k_1} \quad C_{i+1}^* = \frac{C_{k_1} + C_{i+1}}{2} \quad C_{i+2}^* = C_{i+1} \quad (15)$$

In such a way, the number of terms for \mathbf{C} - and \mathbf{C}^* -series is the same and equal to n . The above two conditions on the \mathbf{C} amplitudes are graphically shown in **Figure 5**. Furthermore, a numerical example of the above reduction procedure is reported in Ref. [34].

Figure 5.

The rainflow counting method is applied to the \mathbf{N}^* -series. For each counted reversal, the maximum value of \mathbf{N}^* and the amplitude of \mathbf{C}^* computed as proposed in Ref. [40] are registered in order to determine the following equivalent stress amplitude:

$$\sigma_{eq,a} = \sqrt{\left(N_{\max}^* \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}} \right)^2 \left(C_a^* \right)^2} \quad (16)$$

The damage accumulated during the observation period T_0 is computed by applying the Palmgren-Miner rule:

$$D(T_0) = \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{1}{2 \cdot N_0 \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\sigma_{eq,a}^{(j)}} \right)^{-\frac{1}{k}}} \quad (17)$$

where $\sigma_{eq,a}^{(j)}$ is the amplitude of the equivalent stress related to the j -th reversal (computed according to Eq.(16)), and J is the total number of counted reversals. Consequently, the fatigue life is given by:

$$T_f = D_{cr} \frac{T_0}{D(T_0)} \quad (18)$$

where D_{cr} is the critical damage.

3. APPLICATION OF THE NOVEL PROCEDURE: A CASE STUDY

The case study here examined is represented by the top fillet-welded T-joint on the right-hand side of the H component shown in **Figure 6**, which is the weakest T-joint with regard to fatigue failure under service condition [35], as has been experimentally observed. The welding has been performed by means of a metal inert gas process. The leg length of welding is equal to 5mm.

Figure 6.

Such a component is a part of an arm sprayer, which is an agricultural machine used to pulverize herbicides and fungicides in order to preserve crops against harmful insects and herbs. Under

sprayer service condition, the H component and consequently its T-joints are subjected to high-cycle fatigue random loading.

This component has already been analysed by the present authors in Refs [36-39] considering not the actual random loading acting on the H component, but an equivalent loading constituted by forces with a constant amplitude.

3.1 Multiaxial random stress field

The random stress field in the T-joint has been determined by employing both experimental measurements and finite element analysis [35]. Since a severe crack pattern in the H component is usually highlighted after 2000h of sprayer operation (see **Figure 3**), such a time interval is assumed to be the observation time interval \bar{T} .

A typical service condition of the sprayer being examined, represented by the application of herbicides in crops of a Brazilian city (Jaboticabal, São Paulo), consists of 12 maneuvers repeated many times during \bar{T} . The duration of each of such 12 maneuvers is listed in **Table 1**, together with how many times each maneuver is repeated during \bar{T} .

Note that each maneuver was performed twice a day: one when the tractor fuel tank was full, and the other one when the fuel tank was empty. More precisely (**Table 1**):

(a) Shifting the tractor, dragging the agricultural sprayer from the farmhouse to the crops on unpaved road. The tractor left the farmhouse with the herbicide-tank full and came back with the tank empty;

- (b) Application of the herbicide on the perimeter of the uncultivated field. Only the spray nozzles located on one side of the bar with respect to the H component were opened in such an operation;
- (c) Application of the herbicide on the cultivated area. The tractor wheels remained between the planting rows and, when the machine reached the end of the row, it performed a U-curve crossing the planting rows;
- (d) Braking: this occurred about five times each travel.

Table 1.

Strain measurements have been performed on the H component in some control points [35]. More precisely, two tee-rosettes have been arranged on each chord (see points W1 and W2 in **Figure 5**), whereas two fish-bone strain gauges have been arranged on one of the two braces (see point W3 in **Figure 5**).

For each of the maneuvers listed in **Table 1**, the maximum principal strain time-history has been computed by exploiting such experimental measurements. Note that, for a given maneuver, an averaging operation (due to symmetry reasons) has been performed on the maximum principal strain time histories at point W1 and W2, and one time history has been obtained. The time histories are named $\varepsilon_{1,c}^{exp,m}$ at point W1 (or equivalently at point W2) and $\varepsilon_{1,b}^{exp,m}$ at point W3, being $1 \leq m \leq 12$ the index which corresponds to the maneuver number shown in **Table 1**.

In order to determine the multiaxial random stress field in the H component, finite element analyses have been carried out [35]. In more detail, the forces on the H component are schematised by F_b and F_c in **Figure 5**. The material is C25E steel, whose mechanical properties are listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2.

Linear elastic finite element analyses have been performed through the commercial package Ansys 14.5 (Work-bench 15.0) using SOLID 185 finite elements, both prismatic (8 nodes) and tetrahedral (10 nodes). The adopted discretization is shown in **Figure 7**, where the finite element mesh is assessed through a convergence analysis, being the minimum finite element size equal to about 0.7 mm. Details on the numerical model are available in Refs [35,38].

Figure 7.

Initially, four forces F_b have been applied to the FE model, each one being equal to 1N (in such a case, the F_c force has been taken equal to zero). From the FE analysis, the maximum principal strain at point W1 is equal to about zero, whereas that at point W3 is 10 times greater. Then, one force F_c equal to 1N has been applied to the FE model (in such a case, the F_b forces have been taken equal to zero). From the FE analysis, the maximum principal strain at point W3 is equal to about zero, whereas that at point W1 is 110

times greater. Therefore, the maximum principal strain $\varepsilon_{1,c}^{num}$ at point W1 is only linked to the force F_c , whereas the maximum principal strain $\varepsilon_{1,b}^{num}$ at point W3 is only linked to the forces F_b .

Under linear elastic behaviour assumption, the numerical loading condition to simulate the actual one for the m -th maneuver, i.e. F_b^m together with F_c^m ($1 \leq m \leq 12$), is obtained multiplying the unit value of F_b^m or F_c^m by the sequence $\varepsilon_{1,b}^{exp,m} / \varepsilon_{1,b}^{num}$ and $\varepsilon_{1,c}^{exp,m} / \varepsilon_{1,c}^{num}$, respectively. This operation ensures that $\varepsilon_{1,b}^{num,m} = \varepsilon_{1,b}^{exp,m}$ and $\varepsilon_{1,c}^{num,m} = \varepsilon_{1,c}^{exp,m}$ for each value of m , with $1 \leq m \leq 12$. Note that such an operation is possible since only static behaviour of the H component is considered, whereas dynamic behaviour (for example, due to resonance peaks or damping) is ignored.

3.2 Damage evaluation

Let us consider the polar frame Ora shown in **Figure 8**. The line starting from point O with an orientation α can be considered as a generic extrapolation path according to the structural hot spot stress approach (described in Section 2.1). Therefore, the generic hot spot is the point at the intersection between such a line and the weld toe.

Figure 8.

The stress tensor at such a hot spot point is computed through Eqs (1)-(3) for each maneuver, where the thickness T of the chord is equal to 4.76mm.

The damage is computed through Eq.(17) for each maneuver (the observation period T_0 in such an equation corresponds to the duration of each maneuver, see **Table 1**), and each value obtained is then multiplied by the number of times that a given maneuver is repeated during the observation time interval \bar{T} (see last column of **Table 1**). The fatigue parameters used in such a calculation refer to welding material, and are listed in **Table 3**. The total damage is determined by summing the damage accumulated for each maneuver during \bar{T} .

Table 3.

Both stress tensor and damage calculation are repeated by varying α , with $0^\circ \leq \alpha < 360^\circ$.

The same procedure is performed for the brace by considering (a) the generic extrapolation path corresponding to a generator of the brace cylindrical surface, (b) the generic hot spot at the weld toe, (c) $T = 4.76\text{mm}$, and by replacing $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}$ with $\sigma_z, \sigma_\theta, \tau_{z\theta}$ in Eqs (1)-(3).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In **Figure 9**, the probability density function of the stresses $\sigma_{x,hs}, \sigma_{y,hs}, \tau_{xy,hs}$ (input data of the criterion) and the equivalent stress amplitude $\sigma_{eq,a}$ (output of the criterion) in the chord are shown for orientation $\alpha=120^\circ$ and maneuver $m=4$ (**Figure 9(a)**) and $m=6$ (**Figure 9(b)**). Such an orientation is that along which the accumulated total damage is maximum with respect to the other orientations, whereas the maneuvers $m=4$ and $m=6$ are those in correspondence of which the accumulated damage for $\alpha=120^\circ$ is maximum and minimum, respectively, in comparison with the other maneuvers being examined. A comparison between the shape of the input signals and that of the output signal can also be performed.

Figure 9.

The spectra of the maximum normal stress N_{max}^* , shear stress amplitude C_a^* , and equivalent stress amplitude $\sigma_{eq,a}$ in the chord are plotted in the case of $\alpha=120^\circ$, for maneuver $m=4$ (**Figure 9(c)**) and $m=6$ (**Figure 9(d)**). From such curves, the number of loading cycles for which the maximum value or amplitude of the above stresses is greater than a given value can be deduced.

Figure 10 refers to the brace and is analogous to **Figure 9** but, in such a case, the orientation along which the accumulated damage is maximum is $\alpha=105^\circ$. For such an orientation, the maneuvers in correspondence of which the accumulated damage is maximum and minimum are the maneuvers $m=4$ and $m=3$, respectively.

Figure 10.

In **Figure 11**, the value of total damage is plotted against α in the chord (**Figure 11(a)**) and in the brace (**Figure 11(b)**). An α increment of 15° is selected.

Figure 11.

A critical damage $D_{cr}=0.3$ is considered. As a matter of fact, it has been experimentally proved [41,42] that the critical damage is a random parameter that may range from 0.15 to 1.06. In more detail, the German guideline "Fracture Mechanics Proof of Strength of Engineering Components" [41] and Li et al. [42] recommended to adopt $D_{cr}=0.3$ in design of steel structures, steel for casting, and aluminium alloy for mechanical components.

From **Figure 11**, it can be observed that the total damage is greater than the critical one for $38^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 154^\circ$ in the chord, whereas $48^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 137^\circ$ in the brace. In **Figure 3**, typical hot spots are shown. They have been observed for α equal to about 71° and 110° , values extracted by a digitalisation procedure of failure zone pictures. Since such experimental values fall inside the above numerical α -intervals, it can be concluded that the procedure proposed seems to identify, with significant accuracy, the region on the weld toe where cracks are expected to nucleate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A novel procedure for fatigue resistance assessment of welded joints under complex random loading has been herein proposed. Through the extrapolation equation determined by means of the structural hot spot stress approach, damage at the verification point and consequently fatigue life are evaluated by applying the multiaxial critical plane-based criterion by Carpinteri et al. for random loading.

The novel procedure has been verified by examining a case study represented by the H component of an arm sprayer (used in agriculture) constituted from welded tubular elements fillet-welded as T-joints under the multiaxial random stress field. The procedure has been applied to evaluate the region on the weld toe where cracks are expected to nucleate, both in the chord and in the brace.

The comparison between experimental and numerical results in terms of crack nucleation location is quite satisfactory. The present approach seems to be a promising engineering tool able to identify the region on the weld toe where cracks are expected to nucleate and, consequently, to design a suitable reinforcement of such a region.

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A NOVEL PROCEDURE FOR DAMAGE EVALUATION OF FILLET-WELDED JOINTS

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Three weld stress calculation methods.

Figure 2. H component of an arm sprayer used in agriculture.

Figure 3. Typical examples of fatigue failure in the H component. The experimental hot spots are highlighted.

Figure 4. Hot spot and the corresponding extrapolation path according to the structural hot spot stress approach.

Figure 5. Reduction procedure on \mathbf{C} -series: (a) original series and (b) reduced series for $C_{a(i,i+1)} \leq C_{a(i,i+2)}$; (c) original series and (d) reduced series for $C_{a(i,i+1)} > C_{a(i,i+2)}$.

Figure 6. H component: geometrical sizes (in mm), loading condition and control points.

Table 1. Sprayer service condition: duration and number of repetitions of each maneuver during the observation time interval \bar{T} .

MANEUVERS	No.	FUEL TANK	DURATION [s]	TIMES
Application of the herbicide (cultivated area)	1	Full	180	9000
	2	Empty	140	11572
Application of the herbicide (perimeter)	3	Full	40	18000
	4	Empty	52	13847
Braking	5	Full	10	18293
	6	Empty	93	7827
U - curves	7	Full	150	2400
	8	Empty	39	9231
Travel on unpaved road	9	Full	115	3120
	10	Empty	46	7913
Perimeter curves	11	Full	19	18948
	12	Empty	37	9864

Table 2. Mechanical properties for C25E steel [35].

MATERIAL	E	ν	σ_u	f_y
	[GPa]	[-]	[MPa]	[MPa]
C25E	198.0	0.3	470.0	≥ 230.0

Figure 7. Discretization adopted for the finite element analysis [38].

Figure 8. Polar frame $O\alpha$ and extrapolation path for the chord.

Table 3. Fatigue properties for the welding [35].

MATERIAL	$\sigma_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	k	$\tau_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	k^*	N_0 [cycles]	N_0^* [cycles]
Welding	25.0	3	18.0	5	$5 (10)^6$	10^8

Figure 9. Probability density function of the hot spot stresses and the equivalent stress amplitude in the chord, for $\alpha=120^\circ$: (a) $m=4$; (b) $m=6$. Spectra of the maximum normal stress, shear stress amplitude and the equivalent stress amplitude in the chord, for $\alpha=120^\circ$: (c) $m=4$; (d) $m=6$.

Figure 10. Probability density function of the hot spot stresses and the equivalent stress amplitude in the chord, for $\alpha=105^\circ$: (a) $m=4$; (b) $m=3$. Spectra of the maximum normal stress, shear stress amplitude and the equivalent stress amplitude in the chord, for $\alpha=105^\circ$: (c) $m=4$; (d) $m=3$.

Figure 11. Total damage vs orientation α :
 (a) chord; (b) brace.